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О журнале

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DIAGNOSIS OF PATHOLOGICAL MYOPIA: MODERN APPROACHES AND TECHNOLOGIES (LITERATURE REVIEW)

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Resume. Myopia is among the leading causes of visual impairment globally. High myopia and its pathological variants are associated with an increased risk of severe ocular complications, including myopic maculopathy, posterior staphyloma, vitreoretinal traction, and choroidal neovascularization. This review summarizes current insights into the classification of myopia, elucidates the mechanisms underlying its progression, and outlines diagnostic and prognostic criteria relevant to pathological myopia. Particular emphasis is placed on the role of posterior staphyloma in the development of degenerative fundus changes and its correlation with axial elongation of the eyeball. Recent clinical studies underscore the critical importance of optical coherence tomography and other advanced imaging modalities for the early detection of myopia-related complications. The article also discusses emerging strategies for the prevention and management of pathological myopia, aiming to reduce the incidence of irreversible retinal damage and enhance the quality of life in affected individuals.

Keywords: Pathological myopia, myopic maculopathy, posterior staphyloma, chorioretinal neovascularization, retinoschisis, optical coherence tomography, retinal detachment

ПАТОЛОГИК МИОПИЯНИНГ ДИАГНОСТИКАСИ: ЗАМОНАВИЙ ЁНДАШУВ ВА ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАР (АДАБИЁТЛАР ШАРҲИ)

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Резюме. Миопия дунёдаги кўриш қобилияти бузилишининг етакчи сабабларидан бири бўлиб, юқори даражадаги миопия ва унинг патологик шакллари миопик макулопатия, орқа стафилома, витреоретинал тракциялар ва хориоидеал неоваскуляризация каби жиддий асоратлар келиб чиқишига сабаб бўлади. Ушбу мақолада миопиянинг таснифи, унинг ривожланиш механизмлари, шунингдек, патологик миопиянинг диагностикаси ва прогнозлаштириш мезонлари ҳақида замонавий тушунчалар келтирилган. Айниқса, орқа стафиломанинг кўзнинг дегенератив ўзгаришлари ривожланишидаги роли ва унинг аксал узунлик билан алоқаси муҳокама қилинади. Клинк тадқиқотлар натижалари келтирилган бўлиб, улар миопия асоратларини эрта аниқлашда оптик когерент томография ва бошқа визуализация усулларининг аҳамиятини тасдиқлайди. Тўр пардада қайтмас ўзгаришлар ривожланиш хавфини камайтириш ва юқори миопия билан касалланган беморларнинг ҳаёт сифатини яхшилашга қаратилган профилактика ва даволашнинг истиқболли йўналишлари муҳокама қилинади.

Калит сўзлар: патологик миопия, миопик макулопатия, стафилома, хориоретинал неоваскуляризация, ретиношизис, оптик когерент томография, тўр парда кўчиши.

ДИАГНОСТИКА ПАТОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ МИОПИИ: СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ И ТЕХНОЛОГИИ (ОБЗОР ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ)

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Резюме. Миопия является одной из самых распространённых причин нарушения зрения в мире, при этом высокая миопия и её патологическая форма сопряжены с повышенным риском серьёзных осложнений, таких как миопическая макулопатия, задняя стафилома, витреоретинальные тракции и хориоидальная неоваскуляризация. В статье рассматриваются современные подходы к классификации миопии, механизмы её прогрессирования, а также диагностические и прогностические критерии патологической миопии. Особое внимание уделено роли задней стафиломы в развитии дегенеративных изменений глазного дна и её связи с аксиальным удлинением глаза. Приводятся данные клинических исследований, подтверждающие значимость оптической когерентной томографии и других методов визуализации для раннего выявления осложнений. Обсуждаются перспективные подходы к профилактике и лечению миопии, направленные на снижение риска развития необратимых изменений сетчатки и улучшение качества жизни пациентов с высокой миопией.

Ключевые слова: Патологическая миопия, миопическая макулопатия, стафилома, хориоретинальная неоваскуляризация, ретиношизис, оптическая когерентная томография, отслойка сетчатки.

The present work is a review article based on the analysis of scientific publications addressing the issue of myopia and its complications, published over the past ten years. The sources of information included peer-reviewed journals available in open access, as well as articles from reputable scientific databases such as PubMed, Springer, CyberLeninka, Scopus, Web of Science, ScienceDirect, Google Scholar, and the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ).

A critical appraisal of the selected articles was conducted in accordance with the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) guidelines, ensuring transparency and methodological rigor in the selection process. Bibliometric analysis was also employed to identify leading research institutions and the most frequently cited works in this field. The synthesized results of the analysis provided insights into the current understanding of the pathogenesis and complications of myopia, and helped outline the most promising approaches for the prevention and management of this condition.

Holden B.A., Fricke T.R., and colleagues (2016) conducted a meta-analysis and systematic review encompassing data from 145 studies and over two million participants. In the year 2000, myopia was identified in approximately one-quarter of the global population, while high myopia was present in a smaller proportion. Projections suggest that by 2050, the prevalence of myopia could reach 50% of the world's population, with a substantial increase in the incidence of high myopia. These trends highlight the urgent need for effective strategies aimed at prevention, treatment, and control of the condition in order to mitigate the risk of complications and visual impairment [1].

According to Ko Ono Matsui from the International Myopia Institute (2021), the terms "pathological myopia" and "high myopia" (-6.0 diopters and above) are not synonymous. High myopia refers primarily to a significant refractive error, whereas pathological myopia is defined by specific fundus complications, such as posterior staphyloma or myopic maculopathy, with changes at least as severe as diffuse choroidal atrophy. While pathological myopia commonly develops in the context of high myopia, its complications—particularly posterior staphyloma—can also occur in individuals without high degrees of myopia [2].

For example, in a study by Nan-Kai Wang et al. (2016), the characteristics of posterior staphylomas in myopic eyes with an axial length of less than 26.5 mm were investigated, as they contribute to visual impairment in older adults. These cases were analyzed using fundus photography, spectral-domain optical coherence tomography (SD-OCT), and 3D magnetic resonance imaging (3D-MRI). Posterior staphylomas in eyes with shorter axial length may resemble pathological myopic maculopathy and can lead to significant visual loss, representing an atypical form of pathological myopia [3].

Posterior staphyloma is considered a reliable indicator of pathological myopia and plays a critical role in the development of complications associated with high myopia. Extensive posterior staphylomas generate inward-directed vector forces within the eye, promoting detachment of the neuroepithelium, vitreous body, and contributing to the formation of epiretinal membranes and traction of the internal limiting membrane, ultimately resulting in tractional syndrome. The height of the posterior staphyloma correlates with the severity of choroidal atrophy, lacquer cracks, myopic conus, and defects in the retinal pigment epithelium. A relationship has also been established between the height of the staphyloma and the axial length of the eye, as well as the degree of refractive error. Thus, the height of the posterior staphyloma may serve as an important prognostic parameter for assessing the risk of complications in pathological myopia [4].

A study conducted by Shinahara et al. (2021) investigated the spatial relationship between myopic macular retinoschisis (MMR) and posterior staphylomas using ultrawide-field optical coherence tomography (OCT) with a long-wavelength light source. The study analyzed 729 eyes with high myopia and found that posterior staphylomas were significantly more prevalent in patients with MMR (86%) compared to those without it (61.6%). Peripheral retinoschisis was confined to the region of the staphyloma, indicating a potential role of posterior tractional forces in the development of MMR (Ultrawide-Field OCT Study). Additionally, inward-directed forces such as vitreoretinal traction were identified, supporting the hypothesis of a complex pathophysiological mechanism underlying MMR [5].

In another study, Hiroyuki Takahashi and colleagues (2021) demonstrated that posterior vitreous detachment (PVD) in patients with high myopia progresses asymmetrically. They reported a correlation between the development of PVD, the curvature of the sclera, and the presence of posterior staphyloma. The vitreous body exhibited multiple points of adhesion to the retinal vessels, potentially leading to structural alterations, including lamellar macular holes. Extensive vitreous traction was shown to contribute to the progression of myopic traction maculopathy. Furthermore, macular retinoschisis in highly myopic patients was

more frequently associated with vitreoretinal traction on the retinal vessels. Ultrawide-field OCT proved to be an effective tool for visualizing these vitreoretinal and retinal changes [5, 6].

The Beijing Eye Study, which included individuals aged 50 years and older in northern China, was conducted in accordance with ethical standards approved by the Medical Ethics Committee of Tongren Hospital, with informed consent obtained from all participants.

Based on data from the 2011 Beijing Eye Study, spectral-domain optical coherence tomography (SD-OCT) was used to analyze subfoveal choroidal thickness (SFCT) in patients with high myopia and in otherwise healthy individuals. The results revealed that SFCT was significantly thinner in patients with high myopia, particularly in the presence of posterior scleral staphyloma. Given that SFCT decreases with age and increasing refractive error, the presence of a staphyloma serves as a significant risk factor for the development of myopic degeneration [7].

Ruiz-Medrano J., Montero J.A., and colleagues (2018) proposed a novel classification system for myopic maculopathy, based on three distinct forms of the disease [8] (Table).

The pathophysiological mechanisms underlying atrophic myopic maculopathy (AMM) remain insufficiently understood; however, it is closely associated with the presence of posterior staphyloma, which leads to progressive damage to the choroid and retina. Excessive axial elongation of the eye results in mechanical stretching of the ocular coats, which is accompanied by the straightening of retinal vessels and thinning of both the choroid and retina (McMonnies, 2016) [9].

Table №1

Classification of myopic maculopathy according to Ruiz-Medrano (2018)

Atrophic Form - A	Tractional Form - T	Neovascular Form - N
A0 - No changes	T0 - No schisis	N0 - No chorioretinal neovascularization
A1 - Disorganization of the retinal pigment epithelium ("parquet-like" retinal appearance).	T1 - Internal or external foveoschisis	N1 - Lacquer cracks
A2 - Diffuse chorioretinal atrophy.	T2 - Internal or external foveoschisis	N2 - Active chorioretinal neovascularization
A3 - patchy chorioretinal atrophy	T3 - Foveal detachment	N3 - Scar / Fuch's spot
A4 - complete macular atrophy	T4 - Full-thickness Macular hole	-
	T5 - Macular hole and retinal detachment	-

In the presence of a dome-shaped macula, defects in Bruch's membrane are frequently observed, accompanied by degeneration of the retinal pigment epithelium (RPE), outer and central retinal layers, as well as the choriocapillaris layer (Fang et al., 2017) [10]. As the disease progresses, choroidal atrophy, thinning of the choriocapillaris, and degeneration of RPE cells occur, with subsequent replacement by Müller cells. Bruch's membrane becomes weakened and fragmented, leading to generalized retinal thinning. Spectral-domain optical coherence tomography (SD-OCT) in patients with high myopia and acquired myopic maculopathy reveals thinning of the retinal nerve fiber layer (Koh et al., 2016). However, the most prominent changes include marked thinning of the choroid and choriocapillaris, accompanied by structural disorganization of the retina [11].

Macular retinoschisis is often observed in high myopia with the presence of staphyloma and is more accurately identified using optical coherence tomography (OCT). Retinal detachment affects both the inner and outer layers, leading to the formation of cystic spaces. In most cases, the condition remains stable, with no significant changes in visual acuity or retinal thickness, and progression occurs slowly. However, in the presence of tangential traction from the posterior hyaloid membrane, macular hole formation is possible [12].

The relationship between refractive anomalies and glaucoma has been the subject of numerous clinical and epidemiological studies. It has been established that moderate and high myopia are associated with an increased risk of developing primary open-angle glaucoma, normal-tension glaucoma, and ocular hypertension. Diagnosing glaucoma in patients with myopia presents significant challenges due to the anatomical

characteristics of their eyes, which limits the effectiveness of routine clinical methods. Structural changes, such as posterior staphylomas, and functional impairments caused by myopic macular atrophy, can complicate differential diagnosis and lead to overdiagnosis of glaucoma. Therefore, a comprehensive assessment of structural and functional parameters of the optic nerve, considering the specific characteristics of myopia, is essential for accurate glaucoma diagnosis in this patient group [13].

F. Zheng and colleagues (2018) presented the results of a study analyzing 212 eyes with high myopia (80 with glaucoma and 60 healthy) and 288 eyes without myopia (96 with glaucoma and 88 healthy). It was found that uninterpretable parameters of Bruch's membrane opening (BMO) in at least one meridian were observed in 32% of eyes with glaucoma and myopia, compared to 8% of eyes with glaucoma but without myopia. Among healthy eyes, this rate was 28% and 4%, respectively. In the high myopia group, uninterpretable BMO parameters were predominantly found in the inferior, inferotemporal, and temporal sectors, which is likely related to the increased axial length of the eye, advanced glaucoma, younger patient age, and a more pronounced β -zone of parapapillary atrophy [14].

Conclusion. Thus, myopia, particularly high myopia and its progressive form, represents one of the most significant challenges in ophthalmology, as it can lead to irreversible changes in the structures of the ocular fundus and substantial vision impairment. Current research confirms that the primary factors contributing to the progression of pathological myopia are axial elongation of the eye, the formation of posterior pole staphyloma, and the associated degenerative changes in the retina and choroid. Thinning of the choroid, myopic maculopathy, and vitreoretinal traction play important roles in the development of complications associated with this form of myopia, which makes the diagnosis and monitoring of these changes highly relevant.

Imaging methods, such as spectral-domain optical coherence tomography (SD-OCT), ultrawide-field OCT, and 3D MRI, enable detailed assessment of anatomical and structural changes in myopia, facilitating the early detection of complications and timely treatment. The development of new treatment approaches, including therapeutic methods, surgical correction, and optical technologies for controlling the progression of myopia, is crucial for preventing patient disability.

Findings. Pathological myopia is associated with distinct morphological changes in the ocular fundus, including the formation of posterior staphyloma, the development of myopic maculopathy, and the emergence of vitreoretinal traction.

Posterior staphyloma plays a critical role in the progression of myopia-related complications, as it contributes to choroidal thinning, rupture of Bruch's membrane, and degeneration of the retinal pigment epithelium.

Optical coherence tomography (OCT) remains the primary diagnostic tool for identifying structural changes in myopia, enabling the early detection of degenerative alterations.

The current classification of myopic maculopathy (Ruiz-Medrano et al., 2018) facilitates the systematic categorization of pathological changes and aids in assessing the risk of complications.

Future research should focus on exploring the factors influencing the progression of myopia, developing novel methods for managing complications, and formulating personalized treatment strategies.

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